

ISSN (o): 3030-3362

N^o 7(16)

27.06.2024

RESEARCH AND IMPLEMENTATION
TADQIQ VA TATBIQ
ILMIY-USLUBIY JURNALI

SJIF 2024
5.3

zenodo

Google
scholar

OpenAIRE

CERTIFICATE
N^o 078777

INDEX COPERNICUS
INTERNATIONAL

- ✓ ANIQ FANLAR
- ✓ TABIIY FANLAR
- ✓ SIYOSIY FANLAR
- ✓ IJTIMOIIY FANLAR

- ✓ IQTISOD FANLARI
- ✓ TEXNIKA FANLARI
- ✓ TIBBIYOT FANLARI
- ✓ PEDAGOGIKA FANLARI

fer-teach.uz

@ferteach_uz

Bosh muharrir:

F.M.Muxtarov
t.f.b. PhD, dotsent

Jurnal oyda bir
marta nashr etiladi.

Nashr tillari:

O'zbek, rus, ingliz va
qoraqalpoq

O'zbekiston Respublikasi
Prezidenti Administratsiyasi
huzuridagi
Axborot va ommaviy
kommunikatsiya agentligida
2023-yil 3-mayda
№078777
raqam bilan ro'yxatga
olingan

[SJIF-2024: 5.3](#)

Murojaat uchun

 [@ferteach_uz](#)

 +99893-343-13-14

 <https://fer-teach.uz/rai>

Mas'ul muharrir

S.I.Zokirov - f.-m.f.b. PhD., TATU Farg'ona filiali, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston.

Taxrir hay'ati:

B.R.Ismailov – t.f.d., prof. MAvezov Jan. Qoz. Univ-ti., Chimkent, Qozog'iston

I.Byorno - Ph.D., Imeritus, Daniya Texnika Universiteti, Kopengagen, Daniya

L.K.Mamadaliyeva – t.f.d. (DSc), prof. FarPI, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston

M.E.Yunusaliyev – t.f.d. (DSc), prof. FarPI, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston

X.B.Ismailov- t.f.n., dot., MAvezov Jan. Qoz. Univ-ti., Chimkent, Qozog'iston

J.T.Moldaliyev - bio. f. n., dotsent. OshDU, Osh, Qirg'iziston

T.M.Abdullayev – t.f.b. Ph.D., TATU Farg'ona filiali, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston.

N.I.Ibrokhimov – f.-m.f.b. Ph.D., TATU Farg'ona filiali, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston.

A.R.Nurmatov – tarix f.b. Ph.D., NamDU, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston.

D.F.To'xtasinov - ped.f.b. Ph.D., TATU Farg'ona filiali, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston.

S.B.Atajonova - ped.f.b. Ph.D, AndMI, Andijon O'zbekiston

Sh.A.Umarov - f.-m.f.b. Ph.D., TATU Farg'ona filiali, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston.

I.A.Rustamov - fal.f.b. Ph.D., TATU Farg'ona filiali, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston.

B.X.Tolipov - f.f.b. Ph.D., TATU Farg'ona filiali, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston.

O.X.Otaqulov – t.f.n., dotsent. TATU Farg'ona filiali, O'zbekiston

O.S.Raimjonova – t.f.b. Ph.D, dotsent, TATU Farg'ona filiali, O'zbekiston

R.A.Nuridinova – t.f.b. Ph.D, dotsent, TATU Farg'ona filiali, O'zbekiston

M.I.Ismoilov – t.f.b. Ph.D, dotsent, TATU Farg'ona filiali, O'zbekiston

I.T.Tojiboyev – t.f.n., dotsent, Farg'ona davlat universiteti, O'zbekiston

Sh.J.Kholmatov - i.i.f.b. PhD., TATU Farg'ona filiali, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston

Z.N.Khatamova - t.f.b. PhD., TATU Farg'ona filiali, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston

Syntactic synonymy and syntactic variability

Polvonova Bashorat Mirobixonovna

Scientific researcher of Ferghana State University, teacher of Uzbek language and literature in academic Lyceum of Fergana branch of Tashkent University of Information Technology

Annotation. *This article deals with the issue of syntactic synonymy as well as variability in linguistics, summarizing the history of syntactic synonyms learning, existing problems, views on the phenomenon of variation in modern and traditional linguistics.*

Keywords: *synonymy, syntactic synonymy, invariant, variant, variation, methodological character, simple sentence, compound sentence, proposition, predicative, variation, mold, model, etc.*

Синтаксическая синонимия и синтаксическая изменчивость

Полвонова Башорат Миробихоновна

Научный сотрудник Ферганского государственного университета, преподаватель узбекского языка и литературы в академическом лицее Ферганского филиала Ташкентского университета информационных технологий

Аннотация. *В статье рассматривается проблема синтаксической синонимии, а также вариативности в языкознании, обобщается история изучения синтаксических синонимов, существующие проблемы, взгляды на явление вариативности в современной и традиционной лингвистике.*

Ключевые слова: *синонимия, синтаксическая синонимия, инвариант, вариант, вариация, методический признак, простое предложение, сложное предложение, пропозиция, предикатив, вариация, форма, модель и т. д..*

Introduction. As a result of the structural approach to the object under study in World linguistics, linguistic units have been interpreted as a whole. The elements contained in the whole are recognized by the fact that they define the content of this whole, that the content of linguistic units is formed from a complex of distinguishing and unifying signs, that these signs create an imbalance in form and meaning, that the distinguishing and non-distinguishing (unifying) signs in the content of the linguistic unit are determined on the basis [1-3]. The contextual reflection of the socio-political processes taking place in society and the communicative relationships that arise through them, the transmission of

Tadqiq va tatbiq ilmiy-uslubiy jurnal	Research and implementation scientific-methodical journal	Исследования и внедрение научно-методический журнал
Tom 02. Son. 07 2024	Vol. 02. Iss. 07 2024	Том 02. Вып. 07 2024

information and its reception, processing, use of it for certain purposes, are manifested in texts specific to all styles, in which synonymy and variability between syntactic units are an important aspect, the ability to apply it correctly can decide the fate of Therefore, in each national language section, it is relevant to highlight the issue of synonymy between linguistic units as well as variability.

Although research on synonymy as well as variability is of considerable size, syntactic synonymy, especially syntactic variability, remains an issue in linguistics that has not yet found its solution. This makes it possible to correctly apply text units in Uzbek linguistics, distinguish between syntactic synonyms and the basic principles of variationism, evaluate their formative and content structure, structural-semantic properties, formulate syntactic monoscience between them, and identify methodological-semantic signs of syntactic units, indicating that their study is of particular importance. Synonymy as well as variability, in particular the study of these phenomena at the syntactic level, are distinguished from other linguistic problems by their actuality. This issue has been discussed in detail by many scholars. Including the phenomenon of synonymy in World linguistics G.A.Zolotova, Y.P.Schendels, A.V.Fetisova, L.N.Smirnova, N.D.Zarubina studies [1-5].Synonymy in Turkology Z.M.Zakiyev, S.M.Ibragimov, M.I.Adilov, Sh.V.Yusufli, and in Uzbek linguistics, G'.Abdurahmanov, M.F.Studied in Palevskaya studies. It is found in the work of such linguistic scientists as Jumanazarova. The linguistic research carried out by our scientists has been a worthy contribution to the development of the field of syntax. In extensive research within synonymy and variationism, the syntactic content, as well as the comparative linguistic approach to variation, have not been carried out to this day, which is considered one of the most pressing problems in general linguistics and Uzbek linguistics. But in Uzbek linguistics, syntactic synonymy and syntactic variability have not been analyzed monographically in a comparative way.

Methods. Syntactic units also have types of form and content Relations, which can be attributed syntactic homonymy, synonymy, antonymy, as well as ambiguity as side phenomena, as well as variability. While syntactic homogeneity and synonymy have been considered in most scientific studies, there is very little work done on syntactic units of antonyms and variant phenomena. A. Mamajonov, A.Nurmonov, N.Mahmudov, D.Nabiyeva [6-8]. According to D. Nabiyeva, the **Ppm** (P – proposition, p – predicate, m – relation) model for simple sentences in the language is the main invariant, and the filling of this invariant with real sentences are variants. Each variant has its own transposition, and these

variants are mutually synonymous. R.Saifullayeva uses the **WPm** (Word - word, P - predicate, m - marker) template for grammatically formed sentences, and W for semantically-functionally formed word-sentence sentences chooses a template. And it claims to be an invariant model for real sentences.

In traditional linguistics, variants are recognized as units that are very close to each other in terms of meaning and form. A. Mamajonov in the work «Conjunction Stylistics» if the connection between the components of the conjunction changes with connectors of the same type (for example, only conflicting connectors), the option is a conjunction, if the connection of a different character points out that if it changes with objects, it forms a synonym In the scientific work of the Shukurovs, we can see some observations about syntactic variability[8-9]. The unity of form and content, the relationship of these units, as well as the question of the study of these relations, has always been considered an actual issue in linguistics, in which a lot of research has been carried out. Syntactic units in particular have their own distinct nature, both materially and meaningfully, which enter into a complex relationship. Together with the assumption of one another, a state of proportionality (symmetry) and imbalance (asymmetry) is observed in their relationship. Both cases are considered a necessity, ensuring the survival of language units, the right of the participant of the movement. In the coverage of the topic of research, methods of classification, description, comparison, generalization, contextual analysis were used.

Results. The work relied on the experience of linguistic theory research in defining syntactic units, drawing general conclusions from several scientific views and proving that syntactic constructionism (units) is classified into five types. They are: vocabulary, vocabulary, sentence, compound sentence, and text. The phenomenon of synonymy and the research work related to it have been studied, with the appearance of synonymy at language levels shown through examples. Examples of synonyms at lexical, paremiological, morphological and morphemic levels are given. It has also been analyzed that the occurrence of syntactic synonymy can occur in one or different constructions. Also, a homogeneous explanation of the phenomenon of variability has been studied in traditional and structural linguistics[10-12]. Syntactic variation has been said to be closely related to **invariant – variant** dualism in structural linguistics, where it has been shown that molding primarily syntactic construction is an important factor. Traditional variability, on the other hand, is not necessarily tied to the concept of invariant, it has been found that one linguistic unit is a few manifestations of the substance that are identical, the form being very close. While

the traditional variation consists mainly of two organizers (like a King – King), the structural variants are the complement of a single invariant with infinite variants (actants) in speech. For example, the $W^2 = P$ invariant will be an option for infinite – speech events-real combinations.

So‘z birikmasi invariantlari			
$W^2 = P$			
Bog‘lovchi vositalar turiga ko‘ra	Hokim so‘z qanday turkum bilan ifodalanishiga ko‘ra		Birikish usuliga ko‘ra
1. $W^{kelishik} W = P$	Otli birikma	Fe‘lli birikma	1. $W^{boshqaruv} W = P$
2. $W^{ko‘makchi} W = P$	$W + N = P$	$W + V = P$	2. $W^{bitishuv} W = P$
3. $W^{tobe ohang} W = P$			3. $W^{moslashuv} W = P$

The sentence is given a word addition and a sentence as small syntactic units. Their general and intermediate invariants have been defined. The synonymy of word addition and vocabulary to itself and other syntactic units has been explained, when variation occurs within only one syntactic construction (both in traditional and structural linguistics), synonymy can occur within one or more syntactic units.

So‘z birikmasi sinonimiyasi		
So‘z birikmasi	Sinonim sintaktik birliklar	Misollar
<i>chiroyli qilib turmaklangan soch</i>	1. So‘z birikmasi	chiroyli qilib turmaklangan soch go‘zal ko‘rinishga keltirilgan zulf ajib shakl berilgan kokil
	2. Sodda gap	Sochi chiroyli qilib turmaklangan.
	3. Qo‘shma gap	Ko‘rdimki, sochi chiroyli qilib turmaklangan

Variability in simple statements has been analyzed more broadly than in other constructions. In addition to identifying the invariant and intermediate molds of a sentence, the types of variant sentences are also defined in this. They were classified into FVG, LMVG, MVG and SVG types, with examples of artistic text drawn into analysis. In particular, the lexical material has been proven by a number of evidence that variant sentences have risen to the level of a stylistic figure[10-12].

The variability between compound sentences has been shown to be variously interpreted in traditional as well as structural linguistics. While variant propositions occur between a single construction in both linguistics, in systematic linguistics relying on **invariant-variant** dualism, it does not matter what kind of propositional scheme(s) represent. In it, any orally realizable statement that corresponds only to the **Ppm+Ppm** mold or intermediate molds are variants of this invariant. In traditional views, however, variant propositions are formed when a compound sentence is connected using the same type of connectives. An accompanying phenomenon of synonymy, the phenomenon of sedimentation, has also been analyzed, in which the synonymy-like and different aspects of this phenomenon are revealed.

Synonymous constructions have a certain difference of meaning, and these distinguishing characters enter a graduonymic opposition. The realization in speech of one of the contradicted units is a moderation. That is, it is often similar to the definition of a dominant in a synonymic series, or a nuclear unit within one invariant variant. Hence, moderation is also a phenomenon close to synonymy, or variolite, and this phenomenon also directly connects with style.

Discussion. The results of the study show that within the framework of syntactic units, the role of word addition is determined, and the synonymy of all syntactic units is illuminated from the substantive side and has been proven to be expressed within a single proportion; contradictory views on syntactic variolite have been opened, the phenomenon of variation from the point of view of system and traditional linguistics has been explained, a variant model-invariant of syntactic integers has been developed, variation and the relationship of adjacent phenomena(meaningfulness, parallelism, moderation)have been evidenced by scientific conclusions; based on the isomorphic nature of the language system, it is established that variability is a universal phenomenon that encompasses synonymy and parallelism in its composition, signs that underlie meaninglessness between syntactic units of the Uzbek language, factors and means that cause synonymy of these signs.

Conclusions. The scientific significance of the research results is that the work conclusions reveal the differences of the phenomenon of variability studied in traditional and structural linguistics, determine the invariant (mold) of all syntactic units and complement it with real units. It is defined by the fact that it serves to theoretically enrich the syntax of the current Uzbek language. The practical significance of the results of this study is determined by the fact that it serves to identify syntactic units in the syntactic section of linguistics, to

distinguish their variations and content, as well as to perfect tutorials created in the disciplines of system-structural linguistics, cognitive linguistics.

Acknowledgements. Doctor of philological Sciences, professor A.Mamajonov who closely helped in the conduct of the research work and doctor of philological sciences, professor D.Nabiyeva, candidate of philological Sciences, associate Professor R.Shukurov.

References

1. Zolotova G.A. Syntactic synonymy and speech culture: Actual problems of speech culture. – M., 2007.– Pp.265.
2. Cheremisin P.G. Experience in the study of stylistic synonymy: Abstract. diss. ... Doctor of Philology. - M., 2008.– Pp.265.
3. Shendels J.P. The concept of grammatical synonymy. Philological sciences. – 2012. – No. 1.– Pp.189.
4. Fetisova A.V. Synonymous correspondences between isolated secondary members and subordinate clauses of circumstances in the modern Russian literary language: - M., 2008.– Pp. 210.
5. Zarubina N.D. The superphrase of unity as a linguistic unit: Abstract. diss. ... Candidate of Philological Sciences. – M., 2010– Pp. 973;
6. Berdialiev A. Semantic-signifying paradigmatics in adverbial joint sentence constructions. - Tashkent: Science, 2017. – Pp.250.
7. Lutfullaeva D. Problems of semantic-syntactic molding of a sentence. - Tashkent: Science, 2015. – Pp.137.
8. Mamajonov A. Textual linguistics. - Tashkent: Press, 2011. – Pp.234
9. Mahmudov N.M. Semantic-syntactic asymmetry in simple sentences in Uzbek. - Tashkent: Teacher, 2018. – Pp.110.
10. Nabieva D. Commonality at different levels of the Uzbek language is the manifestation of the dialectic of specificity. - Tashkent: East, 2005. – Pp.248.
11. Nurmonov A., Mahmudov N., Ahmedov A., Solihojaeva S. The content syntax of the Uzbek language. - Tashkent: Science, 2002. – Pp.268.
12. Polvonova B. Grammar of the Uzbek language. Monography.- Fergana: Classik, 2021,– Pp.28.

Tadqiq va tatbiq ilmiy-uslubiy jurnal	Research and implementation scientific-methodical journal	Исследования и внедрение научно-методический журнал
Tom 02. Son. 07 2024	Vol. 02. Iss. 07 2024	Том 02. Вып. 07 2024

“Tadqiq va tatbiq” ilmiy-uslubiy jurnal

Tahririyat manzili:

150100, Farg‘ona vil., Farg‘ona sh., Solim ko‘chasi, 23/4-uy, 26-xonadon

E-mail:

chief_editor@fer-teach.uz

Bizning web-sahifa:

<https://fer-teach.uz/>

“Tadqiq va tatbiq” ilmiy-uslubiy jurnali "Fer-Teach" MChJ muassisligida tashkil etilgan bo‘lib, ilmiy va uslubiy jihatdan Muhammad al-Xorazmiy nomidagi Toshkent axborot texnologiyalari universiteti Farg'ona filiali tomonidan qo‘llab-quvvatlanadi. Mazkur jurnal O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Administratsiyasi huzuridagi Axborot va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar agentligi tomonidan 2023-yil 3-mayda ommaviy axborot vositasi sifatida davlat ro‘yxatidan (№ 078777) o‘tkazilgan.

ISSN 3030-3362.

Jurnal aniq va tabiiy fanlar, ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy fanlar, texnika fanlari, tibbiyot fanlari, pedagogika fanlari sohalarini qamrab oladi. Tahrir hay‘ati a‘zolidan respublikaning turli OTMLarida faoliyat olib boruvchi fan nomzodlari va doktorlari o‘rin olishgan..

Nashr tillari: O‘zbek, Rus, Ingliz va Qoraqalpoq tillari

Tadqiq va tatbiq
ilmiy-uslubiy jurnal

Tom 02. | Son. 07 | 2024

Research and implementation
scientific-methodical journal

Vol. 02. | Iss. 07 | 2024

Исследования и внедрение
научно-методический журнал

Том 02. | Вып. 07 | 2024

Научно-методический журнал “Исследования и внедрение”

Адрес редакции:

150100, Ферганская область, г. Фергана, улица Солим, дом 23/4, кв. 26

Е-mail:

chief_editor@fer-teach.uz

Наш сайт:

<https://fer-teach.uz/>

Учредителем научно-технического журнала

«Исследования и внедрение» является ООО “Fer-Teach”.

Журнал издается с 2023 года, зарегистрирован 3 мая 2023 года Агентством информации и массовых коммуникаций при Администрации Президента Республики Узбекистан (Сертификат № 078777).

ISSN 3030-3362.

«Исследования и внедрение» является специализированным журналом в области техники и охватывает все основные направления исследований и разработок в различных областях технических наук: физике, математике, информационных технологиях. В журнале также публикуются научные статьи по лингвистике, методике преподавания и истории развития технических наук.

Языки издания: Узбекский, русский, английский и каракалпакский

Tadqiq va tatbiq ilmiy-uslubiy jurnal	Research and implementation scientific-methodical journal	Исследования и внедрение научно-методический журнал
Tom 02. Son. 07 2024	Vol. 02. Iss. 07 2024	Том 02. Вып. 07 2024

Scientific and methodological journal “Research and implementation”

Address:

150100, Fergana region, Fergana, Solim street, building 23/4, apt. 26

E-mail:

chief_editor@fer-teach.uz

Our website:

<https://fer-teach.uz/>

The scientific and methodological journal “Research and implementation” was founded by Fer-Teach LLC and supported by the Fergana branch of the Tashkent University of Information Technologies named after Muhammad al-Khorezmi. This journal was registered by the Agency of Information and Mass Communications under the Administration of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on May 3, 2023 (No 078777).

ISSN 3030-3362.

"Research and implementation" is a specialized journal in the field of technology and covers all major areas of research and development in various fields of technical sciences: physics, mathematics, information technology. The journal also publishes scientific articles on linguistics, teaching methods and the history of the development of technical sciences.

Languages: Uzbek, Russian, English, Karakalpak

ВНИМАНИЕ!

При использовании материалов журнала необходимо указывать источник. Авторы статей несут ответственность за содержание статей и за сам факт их публикации.

Редакция не всегда разделяет мнения авторов и не несет ответственности за недостоверность публикуемых данных.

Редакция журнала не несет никакой ответственности перед авторами и/или третьими лицами и организациями за возможный ущерб, вызванный публикацией статьи.

ATTENTION!

When using journal materials, you must indicate the source.

The authors of the articles are responsible for the content of the articles and for the very fact of their publication.

The editors do not always share the opinions of the authors and are not responsible for the unreliability of the published data.

The editorial board of the journal does not bear any responsibility to the authors and / or third parties and organizations for possible damage caused by the publication of the article

DIQQAT!

Jurnal materiallaridan foydalanganda manbani ko'rsatish kerak.

Maqola mualliflari maqolalar mazmuni va ularning nashr etilishi fakti uchun javobgardirlar.

Har doim ham mualliflarning fikrlari tahririyat nuqtai nazarini ifodalamaydi va nashr etilgan ma'lumotlarning haqiqiyliги uchun javobgar emas.

Jurnal tahririyati mualliflar va/yoki uchinchi shaxslar va tashkilotlarga maqolaning e'lon qilinishi natijasida yetkazilishi mumkin bo'lgan zarar uchun javobgar emas.